

Multimedia Approach for Effective Instructional Delivery of Accounting Subject in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

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Abstract

This paper examined the integration of multimedia approach to teaching-learning environment for effective instructional delivery of accounting subject in secondary schools in Rivers State. The study adopted the experimental design with three research questions and three null hypotheses statistically raised to guide it. With a purposive sampling technique, an intact class of 30 students was chosen as sample for the study. Accounting achievement test developed by the researchers who are experts in Accounting and Testing, was validated by three other experts in Accounting and Measurement, and used for data collection. The reliability index of the test which was established using Kuder Richardson formula 20 (KR20), was 0.88. A pre-test and post-test were carried out respectively, before and after treatment of subjects with various multimedia approaches. Analyses of data was done using the mean differences and standard deviation to answer research questions, while hypotheses were tested using the t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that incorporating multimedia elements such as Texts, Images, Audio, Audiovisuals, simulation/animation which may be well structured as narrative, communicative or interactive media in the instructional delivery process positively affect students' performance in accounting education and very impactful on students' achievement. The study recommended that educators optimize the use of multimedia approach in the accounting classroom.

Keywords: Accounting education, Instructional delivery, Multimedia, Teaching-learning, Environment.

INTRODUCTION

The field of education in the twenty-first century has undergone significant transformation owing to the advancements of technology. One of the aspects of technology that has brought about this tremendous change and transformation is the multimedia approach to teaching and learning. The conventional or traditional instructional methods are now being augmented in many cases replaced with multimedia approaches. Multimedia refers to a combination of more than one media type such as text (alphabetic or numeric), symbols, images, pictures, audio, video, and animations usually with the aid of technology for the purpose of enhancing understanding in the teaching-learning environment (Al-Jubouri & Yu, 2020).

Multimedia could be planned and structured as narrative media, interactive media, communicative media, adaptive media and productive media with the aim of supporting the education process (Olukayode et al, 2022). Interactive media is a method of, communication

in which a program's outputs depend on the user's inputs. It allows people to connect with others or organizations by making them active participants in the process through text, graphics, video, and sound. In education, it is meant to engage the learner and interact with them in a way that non-interactive media does not. Social media, virtual reality, and apps are all forms of interactive media.

Narrative media are films and TV shows, novels and plays, podcast, video games etc. They do not unfold randomly, but rather as an ordered series of events connected by the logic of cause and effect. Communicative media include television, radio, internet etc. Communicative media make learners more passive, no active participation, not providing them with ways to navigate through their experiences except for the ability to change a channel. Adaptive media is a media form in which the content itself changes according to a number of factors like the device, the context, the person etc. while productive

media includes wikis, blogs, spreadsheets, apps for editing text etc. and the output from the learning process is the content.

It is important to emphasize that this does not mean that text or audio are not valuable learning media; but simply, that “multimedia” can lead to the retention of the largest amount of information as demonstrated in Edger Dales cone of experience because those experiences near the bottom of the Cone, closer to or including real-world experiences, make use of more media which involve more of human senses; it is believed that the more senses that are involved, the greater learner’s ability to learn from and remember an event or experience. An old-time education adage says:

“Tell me and I’ll forget,
Show me and I may remember,
Involve me and I’ll understand.”

This is in line with Dale’s cone of Experience since at the bottom of the cone where the greater percentages were concentrated, the model allows the learner to get involved with the subject under consideration. For example, the use of text and graphics to present a lesson in a class may not be impactful as when text graphics and audio or sound are combined. Again, the impact becomes more when viewing images and watching videos on the lesson are added. A clip can be sent to students in advance, they can be paused and played at different speed and this gives the students opportunity to revise what is thought. Furthermore, adding simulation/presentation makes it more interesting and engaging. The question now is why the use of one media such as text or audio in the teaching learning environment if students are only going to remember little? It is on this bases that education institutes and instructors throughout the world are saddled with the responsibility of coming up with various interesting methods and approaches to make learning more engaging and relevant to the real world. Almara’beh et al. (2015). It stands to reason that multimedia technology is now a crucial component of all fields of education and training at all levels including secondary education if the system must produce graduates that can fit into the current global

market. A considerable number of young people are conversant with digital technology devices (Internet, video games, and mobile phones, etc.). These devices can as well be utilized in academics and formal learning environment here in school instead of using them just for recreational and social activities. It can be integrated into the teaching learning process to create a more engaging and exciting teaching-learning experience, which will aid in the development of students’ cognitive thinking skills (Wang & Tseng, 2018).

The fact remains that there are more positive results and learning outcomes in a teaching-learning environment where we systematically combine text/graphics pictures or image, audio video and animation as the case maybe for instructional delivery than where a single media is used. When students get engaged with multimedia technologies, Wu and Yang (2015) asserted that learning becomes practical and entertaining, providing them with a pleasurable strong self-esteem. Over the years, technological tools especially the multimedia teaching aids have played significant role, aiding teaching and learning as well as addressing the shortfalls of conventional education approach, though underutilized in Nigerian schools especially in the accounting field in secondary education. In the past, most schools employ the expository technique of teaching because they feel it is easier to manage when conveying information to students but today, multimedia, approach remains the best bet and easiest because technology has changed the way students learn by allowing them to use software tools as well as interactive and collaborative learning platforms to engage themselves far beyond conventional way of learning. According to current research, multimedia technologies have a significant impact on students’ learning as it broadens their learning and knowledge span because of the integration of various forms of digital technology, such as text, videos, audio, and picture etc. into the teaching- learning process, with the goal of encouraging learners to become highly engaged and active in their learning

environment instead of being passive participant of the teaching-learning process (Gordon B. & Gabriel J. 2021).

The same applies to accounting education. According to Al-Jubouri et al. (2020), several studies have established the importance of multimedia technologies in accounting education and its widespread adoption in teaching and learning process. This widespread adoption of multimedia applications in accounting education is as a result of its many benefits which includes the following amongst others: Ability to turn abstract concepts into concrete contents, Ability to presents large volumes of information within a limited time with less effort Ability to stimulates students interest in learning.

Ahmadi and Reza (2018) opined that the use of interactive multimedia information between teachers and students in accounting classes in secondary schools will be of significant benefit to the learner, accounting profession and the society at large. This is because there are numerous transactions in business concern; each transaction when closely analyzed reveals two aspects. One aspect will be “receiving” or “incoming” or “expenses/loss aspect”. This is termed as the “Debit aspect”. The other aspect will be “giving” or “outgoing” or “income/gain aspect”. This is termed as the “Credit aspect”. These two aspects namely “Debit” and “Credit” form the basis of Double entry system. The double entry system is so named because it records both transactions. In fact, the basic principle of this system is, for every debit, there must be a corresponding credit of equal amount and for every credit, there must be a corresponding debit of equal amount.

In order to engage students in accounting education and get them to understand this basic principle of double entry with ease, engaging them with multimedia to execute tasks that would be completed in a real-world setting which will result in genuine learning rather than the use of just words, text or graphs to explain

concept. Furthermore, genuine learning proffers solutions in the real-world situation. For Westberg and Leppien (2018), students will be able to investigate ideas that require learning through the integration of information in real-life circumstances and surroundings, as well as connect with the needs of their broader communities. The idea of realistic activities will be implemented into the multimedia learning environment, allowing accounting students to apply theoretical knowledge in a real-life situation.

Teaching as a process involves sources of teaching, the student and the activities carried out for bringing desirable changes in the behavior of the student. In other words, “teaching” means causing to learn.” Nothing has been given until it has been taken; nothing has been taught until it has been learnt. Multimedia technology brings about life in any teaching-learning environment and provides teachers with the opportunity to know students position in the process, give learners the opportunity to interact not only with their teachers but also with fellow students, even if they are continents apart. They ‘need to be able to challenge and question what they are being taught, they need to be able to draw on their own knowledge and experience, and they need to be able to transfer what they know in real life circumstances. In other words, education for lifelong learners needs to become more learner-focused and centered as teaching and learning are two complementary aspects of education that must work together if the objective must be achieved. Therefore, technology enabled teaching and learning is the sustainable approach. The researcher is taken-up the topic “double entry system in Accountancy” to portray how multimedia application can influence the system. The thrust of this paper is to showcase the multimedia approach to teaching-learning environment for effective instructional delivery of accounting subject with the promise it holds for a more engaging and result-oriented instructional experience which is geared towards equipping the learner with

cognitive, effective and psychomotor competencies needed in the field of accounting.

Statement of the Problem

The traditional approach to teaching accounting subjects in this 21st century is fast becoming obsolete because of difficulties encountered in achieving teaching-learning objectives. The rigorous nature of this approach has resulted to lack of student's interest; inability to absorb and retain what is learnt as well as lack of problem solving abilities. Traditional approach which makes use of text and blackboard appears no longer to serve the purpose in this era of technology advancement hence, the big challenge of how to identify, design and systematically apply multimedia presentations to assist instruction process with the aim of displaying target knowledge and skills in a more appealing way to students. Multimedia is characterized by diversified media types such as Narrative, Interactive, Communicative, etc, which provide high interaction and integration aimed at greatly reducing the difficulty of understanding and mastering concept. (Ningsih, et al., 2020).

These media have not been deployed and utilized to the maximum for educational purposes especially in the area of accounting education. It is against the foregoing, that this study intends to investigate the Multimedia Approach to Teaching-Learning Environment for Effective Instructional Delivery for Accounting Subject in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine the effect of multimedia approach to teaching-learning environment for effective instructional delivery of Accounting Subjects. Specifically, the study will:

1. Examine the effect of text/audio-based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.
2. Examine the effect of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.

3. Find out the effect of audiovisual/animation based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of text/audio based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students?
2. What is the effect of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students?
3. What is the effect of audiovisual/animation based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant effect of text/audio based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.
2. There is no significant effect of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting students.
3. There is no significant effect of audiovisual/animation based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting students.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted mixed method experimental design with the purposive sampling technique. The data collection instruments were Accounting Achievement Test (AAT) designed by the researchers who are experts in accounting and testing. AAT which is scored dichotomously, consisted of two versions of 30 multiple choice items each. The instrument was validated by two other accounting experts and a test expert from Educational measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was established using Kuder-Richardson formula 20, and an index of 0.88 obtained. Before the introduction of the Multimedia approach to the

teaching/learning environment, one version of the instrument (a pre- test) was administered to the intact class of 30 students whose scores yielded the pretest scores. A multimedia teaching platform for accounting was designed and applied in practical teaching and thereafter, a post-test (the second version of AAT) was administered to the same students with scores as displayed in the table below. Data analysis for the study include the use of descriptive statistics (Mean and standard deviation) and inferential

statistics (t-test). A comparison of the pretest and posttest mean scores was done to establish if there was a difference in mean achievement which could account for the effect of the introduction of the multimedia approach. A mean difference greater than zero was considered positive effect, less than zero was considered negative effect while equal to zero was considered no effect. A null hypothesis was retained if the observed t-value was less than its critical equivalent, otherwise it was rejected.

Table 1: Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of Students Administered with AAT

Respondents	Pre-Test (Scores)	Post-Test (i) Text/Audio Based Teaching/Learning	Post-Test (ii) Text/Audiovisual Based Teaching/Learning	Post-Test (iii) Audiovisual/Animation Based Teaching/Learning
R1	14	20	22	21
R2	12	22	19	23
R3	8	19	25	22
R4	18	25	26	20
R5	12	20	24	25
R6	9	14	23	22
R7	21	30	27	26
R8	16	25	28	25
R9	12	24	22	23
R10	15	26	30	28
R11	25	30	21	22
R12	14	23	22	21
R13	15	24	27	26
R14	24	29	25	22
R15	20	28	24	25
R16	11	15	28	23
R17	17	28	25	24
R18	14	19	30	28
R19	15	18	24	23
R20	12	20	27	25
R21	23	30	28	23
R22	25	30	25	26
R23	13	23	24	21
R24	10	14	27	22
R25	9	15	29	27
R26	13	26	22	24
R27	21	30	28	21
R28	12	25	26	28
R29	25	30	29	27
R30	20	26	25	25
Mean (X)	15.83	23.60	25.40	25.47

Table 2: Summary of Descriptive Analysis

GROUP	Mean		SD		MEAN DIFF
	PRE	POST	PRE	POST	
Text/audio based teaching/learning	15.83	23.60	5.18	3.20	7.77
Text/audiovisual based teaching/learning	15.83	25.40	5.18	3.08	9.57
Audiovisual/animation based teaching/learning	15.83	25.47	5.18	3.04	9.67

RESULT

Research Questions 1: What is the effect of text/audio-based teaching/learning on test scores of Accounting Students?

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis

Variable	N	Pretest		Post Test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Text/audio based teaching/learning	30	15.83	5.18	23.60	3.20	7.77

From Table 3, it could be observed through the pretest (prior to treatment) that students mean scores was 15.83 and 23.60 for posttest respectively, while the values of their standard deviation are 5.18 and 3.20 respectively. The low values of SD scores establish homogeneity of the scores obtained in this study. The mean difference between pretest and posttest was 7.7, which is greater than zero indicating positive

effect. In other words, there is positive effect of the use of text/audio based teaching on test scores of accounting students.

Research Question 2: What is the effect of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students?

Table 4: Descriptive Analysis

Variable	N	Pretest		Post Test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Text/audio based teaching/learning	30	15.83	5.18	25.40	3.08	9.57

From Table 4, it could be observed through the pretest (prior to treatment) that students mean scores was 15.83 and 25.40 for posttest respectively, while the values of their standard deviation are 5.18 and 3.08 respectively. The low values of SD scores establish homogeneity of the scores obtained

in this study. The mean difference between pretest and posttest was 9.57, which is greater than zero indicating positive effect. In other words, there is positive effect of the use of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning on test scores of accounting students.

Research Question 3: What is the effect of audiovisual/animation based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students?

Table 5: Descriptive Analysis

Variable	N	Pretest		Post Test		Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Text/audio based teaching/learning	30	15.83	5.18	25.47	3.04	9.64

From Table 5, it could be observed that pretest (prior to treatment) and post-test students mean scores were 15.83 and 25.47 respectively, while the values of their standard deviation were 5.18 and 3.04 respectively. The low Values of SD scores establish homogeneity of the scores obtained in this study. The mean difference between pretest and posttest was found to be 9.64, a very high value above zero, which

indicates a positive effect. In other words, there is positive effect of the use of audiovisual/animation based teaching/learning environment on test scores of accounting students.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant effect of text/audio based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.

Table 6: t-test Analysis on the effect of Text/Audio Based Teaching/Learning Environment

Variable	N	Mean (X)	SD	X ₂ -X ₁	t-cal	df	α	t-crit	Decision
Pretest		15.83	5.18						
Posttest		23.60	3.20	7.77	7.0	29	0.5	2.05	Reject Ho

From table 6, it is observed that the mean score for pretest is 15.83 while that of posttest is 23.60. Computed t-value is 7.0 which is far and above the critical value of 2.05 under degrees of freedom of 29 at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not retained, in other words, there is significant positive effect of text/audio based teaching and

learning on test scores of accounting students.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant effect of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.

Table 7: t-test Analysis on the effect of Text/Audiovisual Based Teaching/Learning Environment

Variable	N	Mean (X)	SD	X ₂ -X ₁	t-cal	df	α	t-crit	Decision
Pretest	30	15.83	5.18						
Posttest	30	25.40	3.08	9.57	9.0	29	0.05	2.05	Reject Ho

Table 7, clearly shows that the mean scores for pretest is 15.83 while that of posttest is 25.40. Observed t-value is 9.0 which is far greater than the critical value of 2.05 with a degree of freedom of 29 at the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected since the observed t-value is so significant that it

cannot be attributed to sampling error. In other words, there is significant effect of text/audiovisual based teaching/learning environment on test scores of accounting students.

Hypothesis 3. There is no significant effect of audiovisual/animation media based teaching/learning environment on test scores of Accounting Students.

Table 8: t-test Analysis

Variable	N	Mean (X)	SD	$X_2 - X_1$	t-cal	df	α	t-crit	Decision
Pretest		15.83	5.18						
				9.64	9.0	29	0.05	2.05	Reject Ho
Posttest		25.47	3.04						

From table 8, it is observed that the mean scores for pretest is 15.83 while that of posttest is 25.47. Computed t-value is 9.0 which is higher compared to the critical value of 2.05 under a degree of freedom of 29 at the 0.05 level of significance. This observed t-value is so high and significant that it cannot be due to chance,

hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative accepted. In other words, there is significant positive effect of audiovisual/animation media-based teaching/learning on test scores of accounting students

CONCLUSION

The appropriate use of multimedia transforms the learning environment from teacher-centred to learner-centred (Biffi, & Woodbury, 2018). It is important to note that the researcher doesn't mean that single media such as text or audio are not valuable learning media; but simply that the use of "multimedia" can lead to the retention of the largest amount of information because those experiences including real-world experiences, make use of more media which involve more of our senses; it is believed that the more senses that are used, the greater our ability to learn from and remember an event or experience (Wang & Tseng, 2018). The reason for this shift from the former to the latter is to create and emphasize a student-centred approach where teachers become facilitators and not sages on the stages, thus changing the role of the teacher from knowledge transmitter to that of a facilitator and a co-learner thereby, providing students with practical experience in every field of learning including accounting education (Gordon & Gabriel 2021).

experiences etc. Educators should embrace and optimize the use of multimedia approach in accounting classrooms, considering technological infrastructure needed to design and create platforms to expand teaching and learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Government should support the implementation of multimedia approach through the provision of materials needed in schools at all levels.
2. Instructors should be trained on the proper use of multimedia.
3. Careful planning and design are essential to ensure that multimedia resources align with the learning objectives, content, and assessment methods of the accounting curriculum.
4. Clear instructional goals, multimedia selection criteria, and effective content sequencing contribute to optimal learning outcomes.
5. Regular evaluation of the effectiveness of multimedia integration in accounting education is crucial hence recommended.
6. Collecting student feedback, conducting assessments, and analyzing learning outcomes improves multimedia design and delivery.

The implementation of the multimedia approach in accounting has the potential to enhance teaching-learning environment, increase engagement, improve comprehension, real-life application, and multisensory learning

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